
**PREVALENCE OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

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Abstract:

Background: Vitamin D has an important role in immunity, skeletal and cardiovascular system. It is produced through skin chemical reaction as well as taken through supplementations. Objective: To see the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in patients presenting in outdoor department. Material and Methods: In this cross sectional study 128 patients between 20 to 50 years of age were included. History about proper diet, income and sun exposure was taken. Vitamin D levels of the patients were checked. Data was analyzed using SPSS 23. Results: Study included 58 (45.3%) males and 70 (54.7%) females. Mean age of the patients was 34.88 ± 7.67 years. Mean Vitamin D levels were 33.50 ± 13.62 nmol/L. In males it values were 34.23 ± 14.16 nmol/L and in females 32.89 ± 13.22 nmol/L. Vitamin D levels were lower in patients who had low income i.e. poor diet and those who were not having proper light exposure. Conclusion: It is concluded that proper diet and proper sun exposure are necessary for normal vitamin D levels. Vitamin D supplementations can help in patients suffering the Vitamin D deficiency.

Keywords: Vitamin D levels, sunlight, diet, supplementations, pregnancy

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INTRODUCTION:

Vitamin D is a lipid-soluble vitamin and has two major forms i.e. cholecalciferol (vitamin D3) and ergocalciferol (vitamin D2) [1, 2]. It has an important role in the skeletal, cardiovascular and immune health system. It also plays a significant role in mineral metabolism. It increases absorption of phosphate, calcium, and magnesium through the intestine [3]. Among the sources of vitamin D is its production in the skin through a chemical reaction. This chemical reaction is highly dependent on exposure to sunlight [4]. Vitamin D is also taken through dietary supplementations. The serum level of 25(OH) Cholecalciferol, vitamin D (D3) greater than 50 nmol/L is considered normal. Levels less than 30nmol/L are considered deficient and level between 30 nmol/L and 50 nmol/L are considered optimal [5].

Currently, around one billion population is suffering from its deficiency [6]. In developing countries like Pakistan, vitamin D deficiency is more common because of poverty, improper diet, and decreased intake of calcium and deprivation of sunlight because of confinement in dark places [7]. Vitamin D deficiency causes rickets in children and osteoporosis and osteomalacia among adults. It also predisposes to the certain type of carcinomas i.e. mammary carcinomas, prostatic carcinomas, ovarian as well as colon carcinomas, etc. [8]

This study was conducted to see the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among the patients with

presenting in the outdoor department and to identify the cause of this deficiency.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the outdoor department of Rural health complex Mandi Sadiq Gunj for a period of three months. Total of 128 patients between 20 to 50 years of age were included. Patients presenting with chronic diseases i.e. joint pains, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and tuberculosis were included. Pregnant and lactating females were also included. Patients less than 20 and more than 50 were excluded. Patients presenting with minor ailments i.e. flu, mild fever, and respiratory tract infection were not included. After informed consent, proper history of patients including demographic history i.e. age, gender, occupation, dietary routine, the structure of house, etc. was taken. Vitamin D was checked. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23. Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative variables were calculated as numbers and percentages.

RESULTS:

Total 128 patients were included in the study, with 58 (45.3%) males and 70 (54.7%) females. Male to female ratio was 1:1.2. Mean age of the patients was 34.88 ± 7.67 years, mean age of the males and females was 34.7069 ± 8.12 and 35.02 ± 7.33 years respectively.

Table I: Distribution of patients according to the conditions.

Condition	Females	Males	Total	%age
Joint Pain	15	21	36	28.12
Hypertension	9	12	21	16.4
Diabetes	12	16	28	21.88
Tuberculosis	4	9	13	10.16
Pregnant	14	0	14	10.93
Lactating	16	0	16	12.51
Total	70	58	128	100

Regarding the structure of the house, exposure to sunlight and proper ventilation was asked.

Table II: Comparison of incomes with sun exposure.

Source of Income	Proper sun exposure or ventilation		Total	%age
	Yes	No		
Low	18	33	51	39.84%
Average	29	9	38	26.69%
Good	2	1	3	2.34%
No income	19	17	36	28.13%
Total	68	60	128	100%

Considering the dietary routine, patients with a low income had an improper meal 1 to 2 times a day, patients with average and good income were having a proper diet and patients who were not working at all were 16 (12.5%) and 20 (15.6%) were having proper and improper diet respectively. In 128 patients Vitamin D levels were 33.50 ± 13.62 nmol/L. In males it values were 34.23 ± 14.16 nmol/L and in females 32.89 ± 13.22 nmol/L. Maximum levels noted were 60.23 nmol/L and minimum levels noted were 15.23 nmol/L. When compared with sun exposure, out of 68 patients who were having proper exposure to the light in their houses, 45 patients were having normal vitamin D levels, 19 patients were having optimal levels and 4 were having lower levels. Out of 60 patients who were not having proper exposure, 2 patients were having normal vitamin D levels, 16 were having optimal and 42 patients were having lower levels of vitamin D. Out of 14 pregnant females, 6 were having normal vitamin D level, 3 were having optimal levels and 5 were having lower vitamin D levels. Out of 16 lactating, 5 were having normal vitamin D level, 5 were having optimal levels and 6 were having lower vitamin D levels.

DISCUSSION:

In this study it was seen the vitamin D levels were normal in patients with proper diet and having a greater exposure to sun light and optimal or deficient in patients with improper diet and not having proper exposure to the sunlight. In our study mean vitamin D levels were 33.50 ± 13.62 nmol/L. In males it values were 34.23 ± 14.16 nmol/L and in females 32.89 ± 13.22 nmol/L. These results are according a study conducted by Gordon et al, who conducted study on health individuals [9]. In pregnant and lactating females variable levels of vitamin D were noticed depending on proper diet and exposure to the sunlight. These results are in accordance with Hollis et al. [10].

In various studies it has been suggested that vitamin D supplementation can help improving the vitamin D levels in patients of different age [11]. However use of multivitamin were unable to cope the deficiency of vitamin D levels. According to the IOM (Institute of Medicine) 2011 report, daily requirement of vitamin intake is 600IU/day. However debate is going to increase the daily intake up to 800-1000IU/day for those individuals who are living in dark places [12-14].

LIMITATIONS:

Small number of patients and exclusion of pediatric patients and patients greater than 50 years of age are few limitations to this study.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that, proper diet and proper sun exposure are necessary for normal vitamin D levels. Those patients who have optimal or lower levels of vitamin D should be given vitamin D supplements and counselled for proper sunlight exposure.

REFERENCES:

1. Pazirandeh S, Burns DL. Overview of vitamin D. Accessed. 2016;10(2415):17.
2. De-Regil LM, Palacios C, Lombardo LK, Peña-Rosas JP. Vitamin D supplementation for women during pregnancy. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2016(1).
3. DiMeglio LA, Imel EA. Calcium and phosphate: hormonal regulation and metabolism. In *Basic and Applied Bone Biology* 2019 Jan 1 (pp. 257-282). Academic Press.
4. van Dijk A, den Outer P, van Kranen H, Slaper H. The action spectrum for vitamin D 3: Initial skin reaction and prolonged exposure. *Photochemical & Photobiological Sciences*. 2016;15(7):896-909.
5. van Schoor N, Lips P. Worldwide vitamin D status. In *Vitamin D* 2018 Jan 1 (pp. 15-40). Academic Press.
6. Holick MF. The vitamin D deficiency pandemic: approaches for diagnosis, treatment and prevention. *Reviews in Endocrine and Metabolic Disorders*. 2017 Jun 1;18(2):153-65.
7. Riaz H, Finlayson AE, Bashir S, Hussain S, Mahmood S, Malik F, Godman B. Prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency in Pakistan and implications for the future. *Expert review of clinical pharmacology*. 2016 Feb 1;9(2):329-38.
8. Weinstein SJ, Purdue MP, Smith-Warner SA, Mondul AM, Black A, Ahn J, Huang WY, Horst RL, Kopp W, Rager H, Ziegler RG. Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D, vitamin D binding protein and risk of colorectal cancer in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial. *International journal of cancer*. 2015 Mar 15;136(6):E654-64.
9. Gordon CM, DePeter KC, Feldman HA, Grace E, Emans SJ. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among healthy adolescents. *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine*. 2004 Jun 1;158(6):531-7.
10. Hollis BW, Wagner CL. Assessment of dietary vitamin D requirements during pregnancy and lactation. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*. 2004 May 1;79(5):717-26.
11. Martineau AR, Jolliffe DA, Hooper RL, Greenberg L, Aloia JF, Bergman P, Dubnov-Raz G, Esposito S, Ganmaa D, Ginde AA, Goodall EC. Vitamin D supplementation to prevent acute respiratory tract infections: systematic review and

- meta-analysis of individual participant data. *bmj*. 2017 Feb 15;356:i6583.
12. Thomas MK, Lloyd-Jones DM, Thadhani RI, Shaw AC, Deraska DJ, et al. (1998) Hypovitaminosis D in medical inpatients. *N Engl J Med* 338: 777–783.
 13. Marcinowska-Suchowierska E, Walicka M, Talalaj M, Horst-Sikorska W, Ignaszak-Szczepaniak M, et al. (2010) Vitamin D supplementation in adults - guidelines. *Endokrynol Pol* 61: 723–729.
 14. Rucker D, Tonelli M, Coles MG, Yoo S, Young K, et al. (2009) Vitamin D insufficiency and treatment with oral vitamin D3 in northern-dwelling patients with chronic kidney disease. *J Nephrol* 22: 75–82.